

EVOLUTION OF THE MONETARY BASE: AN APPLIED STUDY ON THE LIBYAN ECONOMY DURING THE PERIOD (2008-2023)

ABUOJAYLAH AB MOHAMMED DUKHAN^{1*},

JAMEELAH ALAJEELI ABOULQASIM² and HUSSEIN BASHIR ALI ASEED³

^{1,2}Faculty of Economics-Zawia.

³Faculty of Economics and Political Science - Al-Jifara University.

Email: ¹a.dukhan@zu.edu.ly (*Corresponding Author), ²j.aboulqasim@zu.edu.ly, ³alssidhussein@gmail.com

Abstract

The study aimed to analyze the development of the monetary base in the Libyan economy during the period (2008-2023). To achieve this goal, the descriptive analytical approach was used, relying on the data provided by the Central Bank of Libya to analyze the relationship between net assets and the stability of the monetary base. The research concluded that there is a positive impact of net foreign assets and a negative impact of net domestic assets on the monetary base this is a result of the Central Bank practicing a policy of neutralizing foreign assets by reducing or increasing net domestic assets to achieve stability in the monetary base and the economy. The research recommended the necessity of controlling the monetary base and its elements in a way that does not affect the generation of inflationary or deflationary pressures in the economy, and that the growth of the monetary base be in a way that meets the needs of economic expansion and not for non-economic reasons.

Keywords: Monetary Base, Highly Liquid Money, Monetary Policy Tools, Monetary Policy Objectives, Monetary Strategy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The monetary base is part of the total money supply, as it refers to that part of the highly liquid money supply, and the monetary base in Libya represents the reserve money which through it, the Central Bank can control the liquidity of commercial banks and thus their ability to create cash deposits. Understanding the components of the monetary base and the factors affecting it is important for monetary policymakers because of its vestige on the direction of economic policy and thus economic stability.

Base Money (Base Money) is one of the most important monetary indicators that express the banking system's ability to create money and support economic activity. It consists mainly of cash circulating outside banks as well as reserves with the Central Bank. It gains its importance from being the first instrument through which the Central Bank of Libya exercises its monetary policies to control liquidity, inflation, and exchange rate levels.

Since the establishment of the Central Bank of Libya in 1956, Libya's monetary base has undergone remarkable developments that reflect the economic and political transformations that the country has undergone. In the early stages, Libya's monetary system was pegged to a foreign currency (the pound sterling and later the Libyan dinar), and the monetary base was limited in size due to weak banking activity.

As oil revenues have expanded since the 1960s, domestic liquidity levels have risen dramatically, increasing the monetary base as oil revenues have been injected into the local economy. However, the political and economic turmoil witnessed in the country, especially after 2011, was clearly reflected in the stability of the monetary base, as the volume of cash circulating outside the banking system increased and confidence in the financial sector declined, making it difficult for the central bank to manage the monetary mass effectively.

In recent years, monetary authorities have sought to reunify monetary policy and implement structural reforms that include exchange rate unification, improved bank supervision, and enhanced financial inclusion, with the aim of rebalancing the monetary base and adjusting liquidity levels to support macroeconomic stability.

During this study, the behavior of the monetary base during the years (2008-2023) will be tracked, in addition to studying the factors affecting it during the same period.

1.1 Study Objectives:

- 1) To study the evolution of the monetary base during the period 2006-2020.
- 2) To Study and analyze the factors affecting the monetary base during the same period.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. A study by Amal Ahmed Abu Abouda (2023) entitled: The nature of the relationship between the money supply and the monetary base and the speed of money circulation in Libya during the period 2000-2020, Nalut University: Shrous Magazine, Volume 3, and Issue 3.

The study aims to clarify the relationship between the money supply, the monetary base, and the speed of money circulation in the Libyan economy and their impact on economic growth in Libya during the period 2000-2020 through the analysis of the money supply and its components and to identify the important role played by the money supply through the analysis of some economic indicators. The study also used the standard method using the ordinary least squares method through the statistical program (Eviews9), and estimating the equation of the general trend between the element of time (T) as an independent variable, and each of the dependent variables, namely the money supply and the monetary base, and the speed of money turnover, and the study concluded the most important results that showed that there is a long-term relationship between the time factor as a dependent variable for all the functions used for the variables adopted in the study.

2. Amr Hisham Mohammed's (2020) study entitled "Factors Affecting the Monetary Base in Iraq after 2003": An Economic and Accounting Study. Iraq, Al-Mustansiriya University: Al-Mustansiriya Journal for Arab and International Studies, Volume 17, Issue 69.

One of the most important objectives of monetary policy is to determine the money supply at which a certain level of policy achieves economic equilibrium, and because of the relationship of the monetary base to the money supply as it is a monetary indicator, and its role in the economic stability of each country, which is represented in its close connection with the

monetary system, this base is subject to expansion or contraction, and these fluctuations in the amount of money are accompanied by various effects, which may be contractionary or expansionary that are reflected in the distribution of income, wealth, and the level of economic activity. As a result, we find that there is a direct stuckness between the growth rate of the monetary base, and among the most important factors affecting it, such as the money supply and foreign reserves.

3. A study by Ahmed Danaf and Mahmoud Danaf (2017) entitled: Evaluating the Performance of Monetary Policies Applied in Libya during the Period (1980/2015). University of Tripoli: Journal of Economic Research and Studies, Faculty of Economics and Political Science, Volume 1, Issue 2.

- This research paper aims to identify the most important monetary developments witnessed in the Libyan economy during the period (1980/2015). The purpose of this paper is to show the effectiveness of the monetary policies applied during the same period in achieving monetary stability for the country, and this required evaluating the level of their performance in reaching their goals within the general economic policy of the state.
- This research paper, after presenting and analyzing the results, concluded that the monetary policies applied in Libya during the period (1980/2015) were not effective enough to achieve monetary stability of the country, and that reaching a good and effective level of performance of these policies requires coordination along with other economic policies applied in the country, especially the financial ones, and this has been confirmed by many economic studies prepared in this field.
- This research paper also stressed the importance of developing the banking system and changing its ownership pattern in line with the current economic conditions, in addition to the need to activate indirect monetary policy tools by the Central Bank of Libya.

4. The study of Deirdre Daly and Bryan Gurhy (2025). As titled: Building Monetary Transmission in Ethiopia. IMF. July 2025. This paper is also published separately as IMF Country Report No 25/189.

This Selected Issues Paper reviews Ethiopia's transition to an interest-rate based monetary framework. For this framework to be effective, monetary transmission—the process through which policy rate changes affect inflation and economic activity—must function reliably. Achieving this, requires a clear, well communicated policy framework, strong analytical capacity, and continued efforts to address structural features that may hamper transmission.

The discussion revolves around Ethiopia's shift towards a monetary framework based on interest rates, focusing on the mechanism of how changes in the rate affect inflation and economic activity, while considering the role of the monetary base within this context.

5. The study of Dimitris Korobilis (2025). As titled: Exploring Monetary Policy Shocks with Large-Scale Bayesian VARs. Published on arXiv on May 10, 2025.

It provides an innovative framework using BVAR models to estimate the impact of monetary policy shocks, specifically on consumer prices during the period 2022-2024, which is useful for understanding how the monetary base interacts with monetary shocks.

He introduces a high-dimensional Bayesian vector autoregressive (BVAR) framework designed to estimate the effects of conventional monetary policy shocks. The model captures structural shocks as latent factors, enabling computationally efficient estimation in high-dimensional settings through a straightforward Gibbs sampler. By incorporating time variation in the effects of monetary policy while maintaining tractability, the methodology offers a flexible and scalable approach to empirical macroeconomic analysis using BVARs, well-suited to handle data irregularities observed in recent times. Applied to the U.S. economy, he identifies monetary shocks using a combination of high-frequency surprises and sign restrictions, yielding results that are robust across a wide range of specification choices. The findings indicate that the Federal Reserve's influence on disaggregated consumer prices fluctuated significantly during the 2022–24 high-inflation period, shedding new light on the evolving dynamics of monetary policy transmission.

6. The study of Carlos Pateiro-Rodríguez, Federico Martín-Bermúdez and Esther Barros-Campello (2025). As titled: *On the Weak Impact of Base Money on Broad Money in the Context of Unconventional Monetary Policy: Euro Area 2008–2024*. MD, 13, 130.

In its response to the economic and financial crises of 2008, the sovereign debt and euro crisis of 2010–2015, and the COVID-19 pandemic of 2020–2023, the European Central Bank (ECB) implemented an unconventional monetary policy aimed at providing liquidity for more than a decade, through a complex set of tools and operations that make up the so-called quantitative easing. The results of all of them are being analyzed from different perspectives. This paper studies the relationship between a large base money, characterized by a voluminous concentration of liquidity in the form of excess reserves, and broad money (the broad M3 aggregate).

Our econometric work shows a low elasticity of broad money with respect to base money, concluding the existence of a weak relationship between both monetary magnitudes, with a sharp decline in the money multiplier. The demand for money has remained stable relative to its determining variables, interest rates and income. At the same time, some practices related to the handling of excess liquidity by European banks through deposit facilities deserve consideration. We propose strict control by the monetary authority over the nature and origin of the funds that constitute the excess liquidity derived from the ECB's unconventional operations, and over its management.

Research Gap:

Despite the numerous studies that have dealt with monetary policy and the money supply in Libya, the monetary base as the main tool that reflects the ability of the Central Bank to control the Liquidity did not. It is a comprehensive analytical study covering the period (2008–2023) with its severe political and economic transformations. The interrelationship between net

foreign and domestic assets and their impact on the stability of the monetary base in light of the implementation of the policy of neutralization (monetary sterilization) by the Central Bank of Libya has also not been studied accurately quantitatively

3. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Definition of Monetary Rule: The monetary base refers to the amount of money in circulation in the economy. It consists of two parts: **(the currency in circulation and the reserves of banks).**

Circulating currency refers to banknotes and coins held by the public – money that we use in our daily lives. Bank reserves are the cash deposits that financial institutions hold in their accounts at the central bank.

- The monetary base of an economy includes all physical paper and coin currencies in circulation, as well as bank reserves held by the central bank.
- The monetary base is sometimes referred to as high-strength money as it can be expanded through the monetary multiplier effect of the partial reserve banking system.
- The monetary base is a part of the money supply in an economy.
- Economists typically look to more comprehensive monetary totals such as M1 and M2 rather than the monetary base.
- Many governments can manage their monetary base by buying and selling government bonds.

Mechanisms of the monetary base:

Open Market Operations: When the central bank buys securities from banks, it pays for them in cash, which increases the banks' reserves with the central bank and thus increases the monetary base. The opposite is true when selling securities.

Interest rate: When a central bank lowers the interest rate, it encourages banks to lend more, leading to an increase in the money supply and the monetary base.

Reserve requirements: By changing the percentage of mandatory reserves that banks must hold, a central bank can influence banks' ability to create credit and thus the size of the monetary base.

The importance of the monetary base:

Price stability: Controlling the monetary base helps stabilize prices and avoid hyperinflation.

Economic growth: The monetary base can be used to stimulate economic growth during recessions or to cool it during boom periods.

Financial stability: Controlling the monetary base helps to maintain the stability of the financial system and protect the economy from external shocks.

In short, the monetary base is an essential tool in monetary policy, and it directly affects money supply, inflation, and economic activity. By understanding the mechanisms of the monetary base, we can understand how the monetary system works and how it affects our daily lives.

The relationship between the monetary base and the money supply:

The monetary base is the basis on which the total money supply in an economy is built. It can be likened to the "water" that fills the reservoir, while the money supply is the "water" that flows from the reservoir to various homes and streets.

Monetary Base: Includes banknotes in circulation and deposits with central banks. They represent the small part of the money supply that is directly controlled by the central bank.

Money Supply: Includes the cash base as well as deposits in commercial banks. It represents all the money available in the economy that can be used to purchase goods and services.

How is the monetary base related to the money supply?

Money creation: When a bank acquires a new deposit, it does not keep it entirely as a reserve, but lends part of it. This lent part becomes a deposit in another bank, and so the process is repeated. This process is called "money creation," and it makes the money supply much larger than the monetary base.

Money Multiplier: The **money multiplier** expresses the relationship between the monetary base and the money supply. It shows how many times the monetary base can multiply as a result of the process of money creation.

Factors affecting the relationship between the monetary base and the money supply:

Mandatory Reserve Ratio: The lower the mandatory reserve ratio imposed by the Central Bank on banks, the greater the bank's ability to create credit and thus the greater the money multiplier.

Banks' willingness to lend: If banks are reluctant to lend, the money creation process will be slower, and therefore the impact of an increase in the monetary base on the money supply will be less.

Behavior of individuals: If individuals prefer to hold liquid money rather than deposit it in banks, the process of creating money will be slower.

In short, the monetary base is the basis on which the money supply is built, but the relationship between them is not fixed but is influenced by several factors. By controlling the monetary base, the central bank can influence the money supply and thus the economy in general.

3.1 The Monetary Base in the Libyan Economy:

Components of the Monetary Base: The monetary base in the Libyan economy consists of currency outside banks, central bank reserves represented by cash in the Fund, and deposits of commercial banks and other institutions with the Central Bank.

Monetary Base = Currency with the Public + Reserve of Banks (Entire Banking System)
Deposits of Public Institutions and Other Financial Institutions with the Central Bank of Libya.

$$B = C + R$$

Whereas:

Currency with the public C = banknotes in the hands of the public outside the bank.

Reserves = R are banknotes that banks hold in their vaults or with the Central Bank.

- The monetary base is under the full control of the Central Bank through the issuance process and the percentage of the legal reserve, the public cannot influence it but can determine the percentage of its components.

Types of Reserves:

- 1) Legal Reserves: These are the cash balances that the Commercial Bank is obliged to hold from the deposits it receives with the Central Bank.

$$RR = RDD$$

- 2) Excess Reserves **ER**: The amount of cash balances held by the bank in excess of the statutory reserve.

Where **RR** is the value of the statutory reserve, the **RDD** ratio of the reserve, and D is the size of the deposit.

- Maintained by the Bank as a hedge against sudden liquidity demand.

- 3) Actual reserves: **R is the sum of the balances actually available in the Bank's treasury and in its account with the Central Bank, which is the sum of statutory reserves and additional reserves.**

$$R = RR + ER$$

Table 1: Components of the Monetary Base

Monetary Base

Million L.D

Year	Monetary Base (1)+(2)+(3)	Public Enterprises & Other Financial Institutions Deposits with the Central Bank of Libya (3)	Total Comm. Banks Reserves (2)	Deposits with CBL	Cash in Vault	Currency Outside Banks (1)
2008	18,881.6	659.0	12,614.3	12,239.9	374.4	5,608.3
2009	20,462.8	317.9	13,182.0	12,670.0	512.0	6,962.9
2010	22,604.2	919.7	14,075.5	13,228.4	847.1	7,609.0
2011	32,404.5	1,809.0	15,755.4	14,890.8	864.6	14,840.1
2012	34,300.9	1,486.0	19,423.8	17,990.5	1,433.3	13,391.1
2013	36,886.5	1,678.6	21,788.0	20,165.4	1,622.6	13,419.9
2014	38,130.3	1,832.9	19,122.5	17,502.6	1,619.9	17,174.9

2015	41,926.2	1,990.1	16,928.8	16,185.2	743.6	23,007.3
2016	54,597.6	2,120.2	25,374.2	24,779.5	594.7	27,103.2
2017	63,199.9	1,529.1	30,805.6	30,267.8	537.8	30,865.2
2018	61,400.3	1,638.5	25,029.2	23,455.6	1,573.6	34,732.6
2019	60,073.1	1,571.5	21,809.8	19,454.7	2,355.1	36,691.8
2020	66,531.8	1,425.2	25,374.6	24,245.7	1,128.9	39,732.0
2021	60,869.2	1,534.0	27,534.9	24,759.8	2,775.1	31,799.8
2022	64,450.5	2,134.0	30,963.1	28,949.9	2,013.2	31,353.4
2023	94,814.2	874.2	50,786.0	48,870.0	1,916.0	43,154.0

Source: Central Bank of Libya

Figure 1

- Figure 1 shows an overall trend of currency outside banks, demand deposits, and the monetary base with some short-term volatility.
- The value of the monetary base, as observed in Table (1), during the period 2008-2023, witnessed fluctuations between rise and fall due to changes in the components of the monetary base, which are represented in the currency of the public, the reserves of commercial banks, and the deposits of public institutions.
- While in the long term, the value of the monetary base is seen to increase if the last year of 2023 is compared to the first year of 2008, where it was 94,814.2 million dinars and 18,881.6 million dinars, respectively, due to the unintentional expansionary policy of the Central Bank.
- We can also see from the table that the value of the currency outside the bank for the years from 2008 to 2014 is lower than bank reserves and for the years from 2015 to 2023 it is greater than bank reserves, due to the public's preferences for liquidity over deposits or vice versa.

- The monetary base witnessed a decline in 2019 due to the Corona pandemic and the decline in oil prices to \$64, which was reflected in the decline in economic activity and the decrease in the available money in the economy, and 2021 due to the devaluation of the currency, which negatively reflected the monetary base.
- The year 2020 and 2022 witnessed an increase in the monetary base as a result of the exit from the Corona pandemic and the rise in oil prices above \$100.

Table 2: Components of the Monetary Base for 2022

Million Dinars

year	Monetary Base	Deposits of other public institutions	Commercial Bank Reserves	Deposits with the Central Bank of Libya	Cash in the Fund	Currency Out of Banks
2008	18,881.6	659.0	12,614.3	12,239.9	374.4	5,608.3
Percentage	%100	0.12	0.42	0.39	0.02	0.45
2023	94,814.2	874.2	50,786.0	48,870.0	1,916.0	43,154.0
Percentage	100%	0.03	0.48	0.44	0.03	0.48
75,932.6	Amount of Change in the Monetary Base					

Source: Central Bank of Libya

Figure 2

We can see from Table (2) and Figure (2) the following:

- There is no significant difference in the ratios of the monetary base items to the total when comparing the year 2023 with 2008, and this is due to the central bank's policy.
- According to Table and Figure No. (2) for the year 2023, the most important component of the monetary base is the foreign currency and the reserves of commercial banks at the Central Bank.

The cash base increased to JD94,814.2 million in 2023, by JD75,932.6 million compared to 2008.

3.2 Factors Affecting the Monetary Base: (Hisham, 2020)

First: Net Foreign Assets:

If the general situation of the balance of payments is surplus, it is reflected in the increase in foreign assets with the monetary authorities, and thus it can lead to an increase in the monetary base and vice versa, as the deficit in the balance of payments leads to a decrease in foreign reserves, which may lead to a contraction of the monetary base if other factors remain the same. However, this direct relationship between net foreign assets and the monetary base is interspersed with some flaws in some economies, especially oil ones, this effect can be neutralized in the change in net foreign assets on the monetary base, and this process of neutralization depends on the trade policy followed in the country. Thus, it is possible to neutralize the impact of foreign assets on the monetary base, as the State can avoid spending these revenues and deposit them in their accounts with the monetary authorities, and thus foreign assets are offset by an increase in treasury deposits, since treasury deposits are deducted from the size of the monetary base over the size of the monetary base.

Net domestic assets:

– Net Receivables on the Treasury:

Changes in the net receivables to the treasury are the result of the change in the credit granted to the treasury before the authorities. On the other hand, since net receivables on the treasury affect the size of the monetary base in many developing countries, because some of these countries spend more than their revenues, which leads to a deficit in their public budgets, and thus the monetary authorities resort to financing this deficit in the absence of financial markets in most of these economies.

Thus, any increase in the credit granted by the monetary authorities to the public treasury, with other factors constant, leads to an increase in the size of the monetary base, and thus an increase in the money supply and thus to a rise in the general level of prices.

– Net Receivables on Other Sectors:

This item changes as a result of changes in the credit provided to public institutions by the monetary authorities, as well as the size of their deposits with the monetary authorities. The importance of this clause is due to its impact on the monetary base and the organizational structure of the national economy, as the more the public sector base expands within this organizational structure, the more likely it is that these public institutions will borrow from the monetary authorities, which usually leads to an increase in the monetary base and thus an increase in the money supply.

– Net Receivables on Commercial Banks:

Monetary authorities act as a lender of last resort, providing credit to commercial banks in the form of loans and advances to counter any financial developments, and through this process

the monetary authorities can influence the size of the monetary base. If they wish to stimulate the economy, they lend to commercial banks, which leads to an increase in the monetary base, with other factors stabilizing, and thus an increase in the money supply and vice versa.

– Net Other Items:

This item includes all liabilities that are not part of the monetary base, such as capital accounts, general reserves, and certain unclassified assets and liabilities.

Table 3: Factors Affecting the Monetary Base
Factors Affecting Monetary Base

Million L.D

End	Total	Net Domesits Assets			Net Domestic Assets		Net Foreign Assets
		Total	Net Other Items	Receivables to Commercial Banks	Receivables on Other Sectors	Net Receivables on the Treasury	
End of	Grand Total	Total	Other Items (Net)	Claims on Comm. Banks	Claims on other Sectors	Net Claims on Treasury	Net Foreign Assets
2008	18,881.6	-102,375.6	-32,145.5	52.2	902.7	-71,185.0	121,257.2
2009	20,462.8	-107,728.8	-37,593.4	51.9	515.1	-70,702.4	128,191.6
2010	22,604.2	-111,558.8	-42,201.6	0.0	1,053.1	-70,410.3	134,163.0
2011	32,404.5	-107,043.7	-45,563.9	0.0	0.0	-61,479.8	139,448.2
2012	34,300.9	-121,480.7	-48,868.6	0.0	0.0	-72,612.1	155,781.6
2013	36,886.5	-114,041.0	-60,792.8	0.0	0.0	-53,248.2	150,927.5
2014	38,130.3	-87,468.3	-54,964.5	0.0	0.0	-32,503.8	125,598.6
2015	41,926.2	-67,487.6	-44,474.5	0.0	0.0	-23,013.1	109,413.8
2016	54,597.6	-46,279.3	-43,298.9	0.0	0.0	-2,980.4	100,876.9
2017	63,199.9	-43,155.2	-50,999.6	0.0	0.0	7,844.4	106,355.1
2018	61,400.3	-53,526.4	-47,975.5	0.0	0.0	-5,550.9	114,926.7
2019	60,073.1	-52,903.7	-37,291.1	0.0	0.0	-15,612.6	112,976.8
2020	66,531.8	-33,226.9	-36,980.9	0.0	0.0	3,754.0	99,758.7
2021	60,869.2	-275,216.0	-198,686.6	19,850.7	0.0	-96,380.1	336,085.2
2022	64,450.5	-311,070.3	-196,271.5	19,850.7	0.0	-134,649.5	375,520.8
2023	94,814.2	-299,265.9	-160,878.8	0.0	0.0	-138,387.1	394,080.1

Represent good loans and accounts under settlement to support commercial banks ' balances*

Source: Central Bank of Libya

- As can be seen from Table (3), the value of net foreign assets witnessed fluctuations between rise and fall during the period from 2008 to 2023, increasing from 2008 to 2013, where the maximum value of 2012 reached 155,781.6 million dinars before the decline, then it began to decline from 2014 to 2020, where the lowest value for the year 2020 reached 99,758.7, and this decrease is due to the political instability that was reflected in the suspension of oil fields several times, which is considered the only source of international reserves, as well

as to the On the other hand, the increase in public spending and the withdrawal of reserves, which affected the instability of international reserves, then the years 2021 and 2022 witnessed the beginning of the rise.

- The value of net domestic assets fluctuated between rise and fall during the period from 2008 to 2023, rising from 2008 to 2012, where the maximum value of 2012 reached -121,480.7 before declining, then it started to decline from 2013 to 2020, where the lowest value in 2020 was -33,226. This decline is due to the political instability that was reflected in the suspension of oil fields several times, which is considered the only source of international reserves, as well as to the fluctuations in oil prices, and on the other hand, the increase in public expenditure and the withdrawal of reserves, which affected the instability of international reserves, and then the years 2021 and 2022 witnessed the beginning of the rise.
- We can see from the table that the value of receivables on commercial banks and other sectors was zero in most years, which means that there is no credit and gives the impression that it has no impact on the monetary base.
- We can also see from the table that there is a positive impact of net foreign assets on the monetary base and a negative impact of net domestic assets on the monetary base, which reflects that the Central Bank of Libya neutralizes the impact of expansionary net foreign assets on the monetary base by inadvertently reducing net domestic assets by shrinking them or vice versa to maintain the stability of the monetary base (automatic sterilization policy).

3.3 Practical Guide to the Practice of Neutralization (Automatic Sterilization) Policy from the Central Bank of Libya:

Table 4: The Relationship between Net Foreign and Domestic Assets and the Monetary Base

End	Monetary Base	Total	Net Domestic Assets	Net Foreign Assets
2008	18,881.6	18,881.6	-102,375.6	121,257.2
2009	20,462.8	20,462.8	-107,728.8	128,191.6
2010	22,604.2	22,604.2	-111,558.8	134,163.0
2011	32,404.5	32,404.5	-107,043.7	139,448.2
2012	34,300.9	34,300.9	-121,480.7	155,781.6
2013	36,886.5	36,886.5	-114,041.0	150,927.5
2014	38,130.3	38,130.3	-87,468.3	125,598.6
2015	41,926.2	41,926.2	-67,487.6	109,413.8
2016	54,597.6	54,597.6	-46,279.3	100,876.9
2017	63,199.9	63,199.9	-43,155.2	106,355.1
2018	61,400.3	61,400.3	-53,526.4	114,926.7
2019	60,073.1	60,073.1	-52,903.7	112,976.8
2020	66,531.8	66,531.8	-33,226.9	99,758.7
2021	60,869.2	60,869.2	-275,216.0	336,085.2
2022	64,450.5	64,450.5	-311,070.3	375,520.8
2023	94,814.2	94,814.2	-299,265.9	394,080.1

Source: Central Bank of Libya

Figure 3: The Relationship between Net Foreign and Domestic Assets and the Monetary Base

- Table (4) and Figure (3) show that the Central Bank in order to maintain the stability of the monetary base exercises an automatic deflationary policy on net domestic assets in order to eliminate the expansionary effect of net foreign assets.
- The year 2021 witnessed a convergence between net domestic assets and net foreign assets as a result of the Central Bank of Libya's decision to devalue the currency to 4.6 dinars due to the decline in international reserves and to bridge the state's budget deficit and the increase in credit on the other hand.

4. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1) Results:

- As can be seen from Table (3), the value of net foreign assets witnessed fluctuations between rise and fall during the period from 2008 to 2023, increasing from 2008 to 2013, where the maximum value of 2012 reached 155,781.6 million dinars before the decline, then it began to decline from 2014 to 2020, where the lowest value for the year 2020 reached 99,758.7, and this decrease is due to the political instability that was reflected in the suspension of oil fields several times, which is considered the only source of international reserves, as well as to the On the other hand, the increase in public spending and the withdrawal of reserves, which affected the instability of international reserves, then the years 2021 and 2022 witnessed the beginning of the rise.

- The value of net domestic assets fluctuated between rise and fall during the period from 2008 to 2023, rising from 2008 to 2012, where the maximum value of 2012 reached -121,480.7 before declining, then it started to decline from 2013 to 2020, where the lowest value in 2020 was -33,226. This decline is due to the political instability that was reflected in the suspension of oil fields several times, which is considered the only source of international reserves, as well as to the fluctuations in oil prices, and on the other hand, the increase in public expenditure and the withdrawal of reserves, which affected the instability of international reserves, and then the years 2021 and 2022 witnessed the beginning of the rise.
- In order to maintain the stability of the monetary base, the Central Bank exercises an automatic deflationary policy on net domestic assets, which eliminates the expansionary effect of net foreign assets.
- The year 2021 witnessed a convergence between net domestic assets and net foreign assets as a result of the Central Bank of Libya's decision to devalue the currency to 4.6 dinars. Due to the decline in international reserves, to fill the state's budget deficit, and to increase credit on the other hand.
- We can also see from the table that there is a positive impact of net foreign assets on the monetary base and a negative impact of net domestic assets on the monetary base, which reflects that the Central Bank of Libya neutralizes the impact of expansionary net foreign assets on the monetary base by inadvertently reducing net domestic assets by shrinking them or vice versa to maintain the stability of the monetary base (automatic neutralization policy).
- Central banks in developing countries are based on neutralizing the impact of net foreign assets, in order to preserve international reserves, and to achieve the stability of the monetary base, to control the money supply and avoid its negative effects on prices.

2) Recommendations:

- The monetary base and its elements must be controlled in a way that does not affect the generation of inflationary or deflationary pressures in the economy, and the growth of the monetary base should be in a way that meets the needs of the expansion of the economy and not for non-economic reasons.
- Reduce dependence on rentier resources and diversify sources of income in Libya to avoid the impact of turmoil in international oil markets on the performance of monetary policy. and to use the reserves more broadly for economic development and growth.
- Coordination between monetary and fiscal policy to avoid contradictions between them and their inflationary repercussions on the economy.

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